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Deep Trade Agreements and Trade in Value-Added: Does Heterogeneity Matter?

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Abstract

This paper examines the heterogeneous impact of Global Value Chains (GVC) integration on signing deep trade agreements. Following [Fontagné and Santoni \(2021\)](#), we contribute to the literature in two ways. First, we extend their analysis by examining not only the impact of GVC on signing an agreement, but on the likelihood of signing a deep one. Second, for GVC, we distinguish between backward participation (value added in exports that rely on foreign inputs) and forward linkages (value added that is embodied in exports of other countries). We also distinguish whether GVC occurs in goods or services. To do so, we combine the Eora dataset with the Deep Trade Agreement database (World Bank) using a gravity-type model. Our main findings show that GVC increases the likelihood of signing a deep agreement that focuses on goods and services. More particularly, an increase in GVC by 1% increases the probability of signing a PTA by 2.9 percentage points. More particularly, backward linkages (relative to forward) are more likely to affect the depth of the agreement as they increase the latter by 3.3 percentage points. Our results remain robust after running a set of sensitivity tests. In addition, we show that the impact of GVC is greater on the depth of provisions related to NTMs followed by services. When the development level is considered, GVC flows create a new motive to deepen trade agreements between countries that belong to different income groups.

Keywords: Trade in services, Trade in value-added, Regional trade agreements.

JEL classification: F10, F14, L80

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1 Introduction

In the last decades, preferential trade agreements (PTA) have deepened to include policy areas that go beyond simple trade liberalization. Such deep agreements matter for trade (Ahear and Siroën (2017)) and for Global Value Chain integration ((Osnago et al., 2017) and Laget et al. (2020)). At the same time, countries that are deeply integrated in GVC might have more incentives to sign such deep trade agreements to better institutionalize their integration. Thus, our objective is to investigate the impact of global value chain (GVC) integration on the signing of deep-trade agreements, with a special focus on the different types of deep agreements and GVC integration.

GVC in goods and services witnessed significant changes over the last decades. Relying on GTAP database, Francois et al. (2015) show that the ratio of value added to gross trade has decreased over the last two decades, both for goods and services, in line with a growing vertical integration. However, while value added in goods sectors including indirect exports is less than the gross value of exports, in services it is higher than the value of gross exports, indicating the crucial role of intermediate services in the production of goods and in trade. This in line with the servicification of the manufacturing sector (Crozet and Milet (2017) and Thangavelu et al. (2018)) as downstream and upstream services along the value chain might be a source of competitiveness for manufacturing firms. This is why it is crucial to distinguish between GVC flows related to goods, compared to those related to services.

Moreover, Pahl and Timmer (2019) highlight a strong decline in the world backward GVC, measured by the share of domestic value added in gross exports (VAX-D ratio), since the mid-1980s. The substitution of foreign for domestic intermediates accounted for more than half of this decline. Substitution of intermediates for primary factors and changes in the export mix accounted for the remainder. They identify three waves of vertical specialization: 1970–1979, 1986–1994 and 1995–2008. The latter wave revealed a concentration of the vertical specialization process, with a sharp drop for East and South Asia, South and Central America, and Eastern Europe and Central Asia. Almost all countries (79 out of 91) initiated a period of vertical specialization. The latter can include either backward flows (value added in exports that rely on foreign inputs) or forward ones (value added that is embodied in exports of other countries). Backward flows may lead countries to sign a PTA in order to have a more secure and stable flow of imported and low trade barriers. From a forward perspective, the associated flows can lead countries to sign a PTA to guarantee a market for exports. Thus, it is important to distinguish between their impacts on signing a PTA

At the agreements level, despite recent waves of protectionism and disintegration, several countries signed deeper trade agreements over the last decades (Mattoo et al. (2020)). The literature defines the latter as agreements that go beyond simple tariff removal. This can include non-tariff measures, behind-the-border regulations and service-related provisions (such as competition policy, Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS), and Trade-Related Investment Measures (TRIMs) provisions). While including these provisions can be shaped by economic and political considerations, having high levels of integration at the backward or forward levels might incentivize countries to sign an agreement (Fontagné and Santoni (2021)) or to include some strategic provisions that might matter for vertical integration. Against this background, our work bridges the gap between two strands of literature. The first pertains to the determinants of trade agreements. This line focuses more on the traditional economic and political determinants (Baier and Bergstrand (2004), Baier et al. (2014); Cole and Guillin (2015); Egger and Shingal (2021)), without a clear emphasis on the importance of GVC. The second strand of the literature relates to the effects of GVC that have been studied on different outcomes (Ehab and Zaki (2021); Carpa and Martínez-Zarzoso (2022); Ayadi et al. (2024)) but less on trade agreements.

Therefore, similar to Fontagné and Santoni (2021), for goods, we extend their work to services and contribute to the literature in two ways. First, we examine not only the impact of GVC on signing an agreement, but on the likelihood of signing a deep agreement. Second, for GVC, we distinguish between backward participation (value added in exports whose outputs are produced by foreign industries) and forward linkages (value added that is embodied in the exports of other countries). We also distinguish between GVC flows for goods and services given that the latter is becoming indispensable in global supply chains. To do so, we use a multinomial logit model where the dependent variable is a categorical variable (no trade agreement, shallow or deep agreement for goods and services) in addition to a Poisson Pseudo-Maximum Likelihood (PPML). Our data comes from several sources. We rely first on the Deep Trade Agreement database (World Bank) and use our previous methodology (Guillin et al. (2023)) to measure the depth of the agreement (generally and for service provisions). Second, for GVC, we use the multi-region input-output data from the EORA database covering the period 1990-2015 for 170 countries. Our analysis is also extended by examining the heterogeneity observed for different types of provisions, various development levels, and depth measures.

Our main findings show that GVC increases the likelihood of signing a deep agreement that focuses on goods and services. More particularly, an increase in GVC by 1% increases the probability

of signing a PTA by 2.9 percentage points. More particularly, backward linkages (relative to forward) are more likely to affect the depth of the agreement, as they increase the latter by 3.3 percentage points. Our results remain robust after running a set of sensitivity tests. Several extensions are investigated. First, we show that the impact of GVC is greater on the depth of provisions related to NTMs followed by services. Second, when the development level is considered, countries belonging to different levels of development and deeply integrated in value chains are more likely to sign deep trade agreements. Finally, these results also hold when the vertical depth is taken into consideration.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature. Section 3 presents the data and some stylized facts. Section 4 is dedicated to the methodology. Section 5 analyzes the results and section 6 concludes.

2 Literature review

Participation in global production networks is closely linked to bilateral trade. If the implication in GVCs raises the probability to sign a PTA, being member of the same PTAs also favors trade in value added. Thus, we first analyze the effect of PTAs on the participation in GVCs, before presenting the determinants of participation in PTAs.

2.1 Impact of PTA on GVCs

A positive correlation is expected between GVC trade and the depth of trade agreements. The former is measured either by trade in parts and components or by trade in value added (Ruta, 2017). Yet, for GVCs to operate efficiently, some behind-the-border policies need to be addressed in PTAs. First, the segmentation of production in an increasing number of stages of production across borders creates new forms of cross-border policy spillovers (beyond the terms-of-trade externality; Antràs and Staiger (2012)). Second, governments may face credibility problems for behind-the-border measures in the context of GVCs. Third, cross-border production increases the costs of coordination externalities (Ruta, 2017). This is why signing a PTA can help reduce these costs and thus increase GVC integration. In addition, the content of deep preferential trade agreements might matter in shaping GVCs. For instance, adding a provision to a PTA increases bilateral trade in parts and components (1.5%) and re-exported value added (0.4%). Thus, signing the deepest preferential trade agreement doubles trade in parts and components and increases re-exported

value-added by about 22%. Accounting for the depth of third-country agreements increases the impact of PTAs on GVCs (Osnago et al., 2017). In the same vein, Orefice and Rocha (2014) show that signing deep agreements increases bilateral trade in production networks (the share of trade in part over total trade) by 35%. The rise is more significant for trade in automotive parts and in information and communications technology (ICT) products, activities with higher regulation levels, than for trade in textiles. The average effect has become higher in the 2000s.

More particularly, Laget et al. (2020) show that the depth of trade agreements increases GVC-related trade among participating countries; this effect is driven by value-added trade in intermediates. They find that adding a provision on a policy area to a trade agreement increases the domestic value added of intermediates (forward global value chain linkages) and the foreign value added of intermediates (backward global value chain linkages) by 0.48% and 0.38%, respectively. Competition policy and investment are key drivers of the relationship between deep trade agreements and GVC-related trade, in particular for North-South PTAs. Meanwhile, an additional provision in a trade agreement increases bilateral trade in parts and components by 0.3%. The positive impact is higher for industries with higher value-added shares in global production.

At a more sectoral level, Sanguinet et al. (2022) show that, for Latin America (LA) the deepest RTAs (from customs unions to economic integration) strengthen the lower technology-industry suppliers. They find higher elasticities when LA countries are exporters in GVC and a higher effect of deep agreements, which underlines the role of LA as a global supplier (forward linkages). Shallow agreements reinforce the value-added importer's role of LA in GVCs (backward linkages). The authors conclude that PTAs strengthen the regional position of LA as a global source of low R&D industries. The network of PTAs between LA and the international divers in GVCs limits opportunities for a change in the composition (diversification) of value-added trade.

A recent paper by Bondi et al. (2025) analyzes the impact of GVC participation on the content of PTAs, using the presence and number of ports, along with the growing size of container ships over time, as proxies for trade in value added. The authors find that greater GVC participation increases the likelihood that FTAs include provisions related to product standards, investment, services, and competition policy.

When it comes to the difference between goods and services, the latter sparked interest in recent decades. It is important first to distinguish between servitization¹ that refers to the shift toward services (and the corresponding deindustrialization that could happen) and servicification that

¹See Crozet and Milet (2017), for the case of French firms.

means that manufacturing activities increasingly depend on services. Few papers have analyzed the latter phenomenon in trade agreements (Guillin et al. (2023)). For instance, Díaz-Mora et al. (2022) estimate the impact of signing new deep trade agreements (DTAs) with services provisions and the effect of the level of depth of these agreements on bilateral foreign services value added embodied in manufacturing exports (GVC-related servicification). They find that both new and deeper service DTAs boost embodied services value added. As for the signing of new arrangements, they show a phase-in period before full implementation of the new regulation. As for the level of depth of new and deeper services DTAs, they show both contemporaneous and lagged positive effects. Finally, they find a servicification-enhancing effect of services DTAs only for embodied services value added from EU countries.

In the same line of thought, Thangavelu et al. (2018) measure domestic servicification as the ratio of domestic service value-added content in manufacturing exports and foreign servicification as the share of foreign service value-added content in manufacturing exports. They calculate GVC participation as the sum of foreign value-added share in exports (backward participation) and the share of domestic value added in intermediate exports for third countries (forward participation). They show a positive effect of GVC position on domestic servicification, and a negative impact of foreign servicification: upstream countries in GVCs tend to substitute imported service inputs for domestic services in manufacturing production. However, for Asian countries, the GVC participation index has a negative impact on the domestic servicification and a positive effect on the foreign servicification.

Finally, Borchert and Di Ubaldo (2021) highlight that joining a services PTA increases the within-PTA services VA share by 0.0126%. The impact of bilateral agreements is twice as large on the VA share from PTA partners, economies tend to import relatively more foreign services value added from within services PTAs. They also find that individual PTA provisions that relate to investment flows and the movement of people are associated with higher foreign services value added from PTA partners.

In a nutshell, the literature converged to the fact that deep trade agreements do increase GVC integration, though with some heterogeneity observed for goods vs. services and for backward vs. forward linkages. We aim at exploring these heterogeneities in our analysis.

2.2 Determinants of the signature of PTA

As we are interested in the effect of GVC on PTA, it is crucial to analyze the main determinants of signing a trade agreement. The seminal paper was proposed by [Baier and Bergstrand \(2004\)](#). The authors show that the likelihood that a given pair countries sign a PTA is higher the closer geographically the two partners; the more remote the natural pair is from third countries; the larger and more similar economically (measured with their GDP) the two traders are, so that they can exploit scale economies linked to the production of differentiated products; the greater the difference in relative factor endowments of the members compared to the rest of the world, reducing the inter-industry trade diversion. [Baier et al. \(2014\)](#) extend this initial cross-sectional analysis to a panel of 146 countries. Their main findings remain robust. In addition, they show that the probability of a PTA between countries i and j is 50 times higher if either already has an agreement with a third country k (“own-FTA effect”) than if the existing PTA links two third countries k and l (“cross-FTA effect”).

Two characteristics increase the benefits of forming a PTA with a specific partner. First, trade intensity suggests that the two countries are “natural” trade partners. Second, comparative advantage, at the task level, generates complementarities in production or consumption and increases the benefit of forming a PTA. For GVCs, proximity matters in selecting PTA partners because face-to-face communication is relevant in managing supply chains and to have a more timely provision of inputs. Hence, GVCs require deep agreements to function smoothly, so policy preferences of partner countries should be similar to minimize the coordination costs ([Ruta, 2017](#)).

Using spatial econometrics with a dynamic analysis in cross-section with Bayesian techniques, [Egger and Larch \(2008\)](#) find evidence that the formation and enlargement of PTAs create an incentive for outsider country-pair to join the existing PTA or to find another PTA in response. This effect decreases with distance. Using a broader sample of PTAs than the previous authors, and also with a spatial lag, [Baldwin and Jaimovich \(2012\)](#) show that countries sign PTA, for defensive reasons, to reduce discrimination created by previous PTAs concluded among their trade partners (domino effect). The degree of contagion of PTAs is related to the size of partners’ markets.

More recently, [Blöthner and Larch \(2022\)](#) apply machine learning techniques to improve predictive performance relative to traditional probit models. Using the same specification as [Baier and Bergstrand \(2004\)](#), they confirm the relevance of standard determinants, while highlighting a declining role for distance and an increasing importance of GDP, consistent with the growing

heterogeneity among PTA signatories.

In addition to the aforementioned factors (geography, economic size and similarity, relative factor endowments), [Bergstrand et al. \(2016\)](#) add political and historical determinants (interdependence or contagion in PTA formation). All these factors explain the probability to enter a PTA, in a given year. Their duration analysis specification explains 26%, 46%, and 57% of the PTA events within 1, 5, and 10 years.

As for the impact of participation in global value chains, [Orefice and Rocha \(2014\)](#) find a positive and significant impact of production networks on the degree of depth on newly signed agreements. A 10% rise in the share of parts and component trade increases the depth of an agreement by around 30 percentage points if countries belong to different income levels compared to agreements between nations with similar income levels (6%). This positive impact is mainly driven by the Asian region. In the same vein, [Fontagné and Santoni \(2021\)](#) estimate the probability that a pair of countries signs a PTA, relying on the determinants identified by [Baier and Bergstrand \(2004\)](#) and introducing two additional variables: the number of shared external trade agreements, and the number of PTAs each country has signed with all other partners. Their results show that bilateral involvement in GVCs is a significant predictor of PTA formation. When it comes to services, [Cole and Guillin \(2015\)](#) examine whether the determinants of signing trade agreements that include service provisions—Economic Integration Agreements (EIAs)—differ from those linked to goods-only PTAs. They consider three scenarios: EIAs signed independently, EIAs signed after a PTA (using a probit model), and the joint decision to sign both an EIA and an FTA, accounting for potential correlation between the two choices. Their findings suggest that distance and the notion of “natural partners” are less influential for services trade than for goods. In contrast, similarities in economic development and factor endowments play a greater role in the formation of EIAs. Similarly, [Egger and Shingal \(2021\)](#) show that the probability for two nations to sign a service trade agreement (STA) raises with the similarity of their service trade restrictiveness and the share of services costs in goods production. More services-trade-remote economies are more likely to negotiate STA. The usual determinants also apply for STA.

Against this background, we extend the work of [Fontagné and Santoni \(2021\)](#) in two ways. First, we examine not only the impact of GVC on signing an agreement, but on the likelihood of signing a deep agreement. Second, for GVC, we distinguish between backward participation (value added in exports whose outputs are produced by foreign industries) and forward linkages (value added that is embodied in the exports of other countries). We also distinguish between GVC flows

for goods and services. Our analysis is also extended by examining the heterogeneity observed for different types of provisions, various development levels, and depth measures.

3 Methodology and Data

Our analysis relies on [Baier et al. \(2014\)](#) and [Fontagné and Santoni \(2021\)](#). Five categories of drivers for signing preferential trade agreements (PTA) are taken into account: i) geographical, ii) economic, iii) factor endowments, iv) negotiation experience of countries and v) participation in global value chains. The first three categories are derived from [Baier and Bergstrand \(2004\)](#), while the last two are based on [Fontagné and Santoni \(2021\)](#). According to the former, the greater the expected gains from a trade agreement (the lower the trade diversion), the closer the signatory countries are geographically and in terms of economic size, and the greater the differences in their factor endowments, so that they specialize in different types of production.

Thus, we run the following specification:

$$Depth_{ijt} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_{ij,t-5} + \alpha_2 \overline{X_{ij}} + \alpha_3 GVC_{ij,t-5} + \delta_t + \epsilon_{ijt} \quad (1)$$

where δ_t represents a set of year fixed effects and ϵ_{ijt} is the discrepancy term.

$Depth_{ijt}$ is a categorical variable that takes the value of 0 if there is no agreement, 1 if the agreement focuses on goods, 2 if it is shallow and focuses on goods and services, 3 if it is deep and focuses on both goods and services. The depth variable is measured following the same approach that we adopt in [Guillin et al. \(2023\)](#) where a deep trade agreement contains a higher share of legally enforceable policy areas than a shallow one. To distinguish between these different types of agreements, we consider the following measure:

$$Depth_{le}^{max} = \frac{N^{le}}{maxN} \quad (2)$$

with, N^{le} the number of legally enforceable policy areas and N , the number of policy areas.² We define an agreement as "deep" as long as $Depth_{le}^{max}$ is above the median; while an agreement is "shallow" when this measure is below the median.

Our control variables $X_{ij,t-5}$ include gravity-type controls as follows. $GDP_{ij,t-5}^{Similarity}$ is the market size similarity between the two countries and $GDP_{ij,t-5}^{Sum}$, the overall market size for both

²In total, 52 single items, or provisions, have been considered.

countries, as follows:

$$GDP_{ij,t-5}^{Similarity} = \log\left[1 - \left(\frac{GDP_{i,t-5}}{GDP_{i,t-5} + GDP_{j,t-5}}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{GDP_{j,t-5}}{GDP_{i,t-5} + GDP_{j,t-5}}\right)^2\right] \quad (3)$$

$$GDP_{ij,t-5}^{Sum} = \log(GDP_{i,t-5}) + \log(GDP_{j,t-5}) \quad (4)$$

For the factor endowments variables, $DKL_{ij,t-5}$ is the log of the absolute difference in capital-labor ratios between the two countries and $SQDKL_{ij,t-5}$ is the square of this variable.³ Our sample includes 170 countries that are present in both databases mentioned above, covering the period from 1990 to 2015.

Thirdly, we calculate two geographical variables, $Natural_{ij}$ captures whether the partners are natural partners due to their geographical proximity, while $Remote_{ij}$ measures the position of this pair of countries in relation to the rest of the world.

$$Natural_{ij} = \log\left(\frac{1}{dist_{ij}}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$Remote_{ij} = 0.5 * \left[\log\frac{\sum_{k \neq j} dist_{ik}}{n-1} + \log\frac{\sum_{k \neq i} dist_{jk}}{n-1}\right] \quad (6)$$

Among the control variables, we also take into account the number of trade agreements each country signs each year as a measure of experience in trade negotiations (Baier et al., 2014). Finally, following Wooldridge (2010), we include the average of each covariate \bar{X}_{ij} by country pairs to control for the potential collinearity of time-variant variables with unobservables that are time-invariant. Finally,

In terms of estimation method, as we are running a gravity-type equation, we opt for a Poisson Pseudo-Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimation method that controls for zero trade flows and for the heteroscedasticity that can affect our estimates (Silva and Tenreyro (2006) and Yotov et al. (2016)). Thus, we run the following specification:

$$Depth_{ijt} = \exp[\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{ij,t-5} + \beta_2 \bar{X}_{ij} + \beta_3 GVC_{ij,t-5} + \delta_t] + \epsilon_{ijt} \quad (7)$$

Two empirical remarks are worthy to mention. First, our GVC variables is introduced in different ways: total GVC, backward GVC and forward GVC. In each case, we distinguish between

³The capital-labor ratio is measured as capital stock divided by the number of persons engaged for each country and year.

overall GVC, those that are goods related and services related. Thus, we end up having nine variables that measure different aspects of GVC. Second, we use a 5-year lags for all time-varying variables to reduce further the endogeneity bias.

As a robustness check, we run a battery of alternative specifications. First, we change our depth variable by constructing an index that compares legally enforceable to non-legally enforceable provisions as follows $Depth_{le}$:

$$Depth_{le} = \frac{N^{le}}{(N^{le} + N^{ne})} \quad (8)$$

where N^{ne} , the number of non-legally enforceable provisions.

Second, for GVC, instead of using the level of GVC variables, we replace them with the share in the bilateral trade that takes place between the two countries. This helps us examine GVC flows in relative terms.

Third, we change the estimation method by using a probit model where the dependent variable takes the value of 1 if the agreement is deep (for goods and services) and zero otherwise. We also run a high-dimension fixed effect estimation with a range of various fixed effects (exporter-time, importer-time and country pair fixed effects) as suggested by the gravity literature.

The analysis is also extended in three ways. First, the development level can moderate the impact of GVC on the depth of trade agreements given that, on average, trade agreements are deeper in developed countries than in developing ones. Second, while calculating the depth of the agreement, it is important to consider the heterogeneity of the provisions that might be sensitive to GVC integration. In other words, we investigate which types of provisions are affected by GVC (those related to services, non-tariff measures, institutions, economic cooperation, those within or beyond the WTO scope). Finally, the literature shows that the agreement depth can have different dimensions. Thus, we distinguish between horizontal depth (that refers to whether trade agreements go beyond the simple tariff reduction) and vertical depth (whether they include legally enforceable provisions that deepen countries integration).

Our main source is the Eora global supply chain database that provides information about value-added and GVC participation in bilateral sectoral exports from 1990 to 2015 for 186 countries (see [Lenzen et al. \(2013\)](#), [Borin and Mancini \(2017\)](#) and [Borin and Mancini \(2023\)](#) for more details).⁴

⁴The list of all sectors is: 1- Agriculture; 2- Fishing; 3- Mining and Quarrying; 4- Food and Beverages; 5- Textiles and Wearing Apparel; 6- Wood and Paper; 7- Petroleum, Chemical and Non-Metallic Mineral Products; 8- Metal Products; 9- Electrical and Machinery; 10- Transport Equipment; 11- Other Manufacturing; 12- Recycling; 13- Electricity, Gas and Water; 14- Construction; 15- Maintenance and Repair; 16- Wholesale Trade; 17- Retail Trade;

Four variables in particular were used: bilateral gross exports, GVC-related trade (GVC), GVC-backward (GVCB) and GVC-forward (GVCF) at the sectoral level. Data for services (sectors 14 to 23) are aggregated, as are those for manufacturing (other sectors). Secondly, the Penn World Tables were used to generate variables relating to economic determinants and factor endowments. Thirdly, data on distance from the CEPII gravity dataset allow us to calculate the two geographical variables [5](#).

To have a flavor of our data, [Figure 1](#) shows the evolution of both deep and shallow agreements over time. Whereas, in the 1990's, the share of shallow agreements was higher than deep ones, deep agreements have been dominant starting 2000's. This confirms to what extent the simple tariff liberalization was necessary but not sufficient to promote international trade ([Anderson and Van Wincoop \(2004\)](#)). In terms of the content of the agreement, [Figure 2](#) confirms that, on average, the number of provisions included in deep agreements is higher for provisions that fall within (WTO+) and beyond (WTOX) the WTO scope. On the one hand, WTO+ includes articles related mainly to services and non-tariff measures. On the other hand, WTOX includes broader issues such as competition, SMEs support, institutions, and general economic cooperation.

Finally, [Figure 3](#) shows the association between our two variables of interest, namely GVC and the depth of the agreement. Three remarks are worthy to be mentioned. For all types of GVC (overall, backward and forward), deeper agreements are associated with a higher level of GVC integration. Generally, GVC is 1.5 time higher in the case of deep agreements compared to shallow ones. Second, while GVC-related flows are higher for goods than for services, the depth of the agreements is also higher for the former than for the latter. This can be due to the fact that, with the goods liberalization, services remain more protected and regulated, especially in developing countries. Third, this simple association shows also that both the agreement depth and backward flows are higher compared with forward ones. The next section empirically tests these stylized facts.

18- Hotels and Restaurants; 19- Transport; 20- Post and Telecommunications; 21- Financial Intermediation and Business Activities; 22- Public Administration; 23- Education, Health and Other Services; 24- Private Households; 25- Others; 26- Re-export and Re-import.

⁵See [Table A.1](#) for detailed descriptive statistics for all variables

Figure 1: Evolution of Deep and Shallow Agreements

Source: Authors' own elaboration using DTA

Figure 2: Deep vs. Shallow Agreements and Provisions Types

Source: Authors' own elaboration using DTA

Figure 3: GVC and Deep vs. Shallow Agreements

Source: Authors' own elaboration using DTA and EORA data

4 Empirical Results

4.1 Baseline Specification

Table 1 presents our baseline regression for both the multinomial logit and the PPML regressions. The multinomial regressions, where the reference category is no agreement, show that being involved in GVCs reduces the likelihood of signing an agreement that focuses only on goods. This result holds for all the GVC measurements (including goods and services, backward and forward). This result seems to be counter-intuitive and needs further investigation. However, while the impact of GVC on shallow agreements is globally insignificant, that on deep ones that focus on goods and services is positive and statistically significant. This is in line with the arguments advanced by Osnago et al. (2017), who confirm the relevance of deep agreements in boosting GVC trade. Several reasons can explain this impact. First, since GVC are sensitive to behind-the-border policies, the latter can be limited in the presence of a PTA (Ruta, 2017). In fact, Antràs and Staiger (2012) show that behind-the-border policies can create cross-border spillovers in an internationally fragmented production. Second, if the GVC trade is high, trade partners tend to formalize and institutionalize their cooperation through a deep trade agreement to guarantee the resilience and stability of the supply chain. Third, as GVC are heavily relying on services, trade agreements should be deep to go beyond the simple tariff removal on goods. Finally, deep trade agreements increase the credibility of the governments involved and reflect the good quality of their institutions that are an important determinant of GVC (Antràs (2015) and Dollar et al. (2016)). These factors explain why GVC can increase the demand for deep trade agreements.

A more detailed investigation of the impact of GVC on signing a deep trade agreement shows that backward linkages have a stronger impact on signing a PTA, relative to forward ones. As countries aim to have resilient supply chains, imported inputs are needed for the whole production process. This is why when countries are involved in backward GVC flows, they are more likely to sign a PTA (see column 1 in Table 1). This result is in line with the findings of Tian et al. (2022) who argue that backward GVC participation provides more upgrading opportunities and thus is more essential for the value chain.

When comparing goods to services, services inputs matter more than those related to goods (similar results are obtained when we compare backward and forward GVC in services to goods). The importance of services for the manufacturing sector has been well documented in the literature on the servicification of the manufacturing sector. Indeed, the latter is becoming more intensive in

services and its competitiveness largely hinges on the services competitiveness (Crozet and Milet (2017) and Thangavelu et al. (2018)). This is why, given the importance of services for the stability of the value chain, countries might be more eager to sign deep PTA that include provisions related to both goods and services.

The second part of Table 1 runs the same regressions using a Poisson-Pseudo Maximum Likelihood estimation method and confirms the positive impact of GVC on signing a deep agreement. Our findings show that an increase in GVC flows by 1% increases the probability of signing a PTA by 2.9 percentage points. In addition, the impact of backward linkages is still positive and significant, with a higher coefficient for backward services related flows compared to those goods related. More particularly, backward linkages (relative to forward) are more likely to affect the depth of the agreement as they increase the latter by 3.3 percentage points. Yet, forward GVC is barely significant at 10% (for overall flows and for goods, with an insignificant impact of GVC forward related to service flows).

Thus, from these baseline regressions, one can argue that GVC in general and especially those related to backward linkages and to services matter in signing deep trade agreements that go beyond goods.

The results of our control variables are presented in Table A.2. Three results are worth noting. First, in different estimation types, the difference in endowments does not matter in signing various agreements. Therefore, while the factor content theory might not be a significant determinant to sign an agreement, factors pertaining to the new trade theory (distance, market size, etc.) hold. Second, the number of RTAs for the exporter and the importer is positive and statistically significant. As this variable is a proxy for the openness policy of the country, it shows that countries with higher number of PTAs are more likely to sign both shallow and deep agreements (with a higher coefficient for the latter), as suggested by Baldwin and Jaimovich (2012). Finally, in line with Baier and Bergstrand (2004), remoteness increases the likelihood of signing an agreement.

4.2 Robustness Checks

To test the robustness of our results, we change the estimation method, the dependent variable, and the main independent variable of interest. Table 2 presents the results with three different estimation methods. The first column reports the result of the probit model where the dependent variable takes the value of 1 if the agreement is deep and concerns goods and services and zero otherwise. The second column has the same dependent variable but runs a linear probability

model as it allows us to obtain elasticities. Finally, the last one runs a high dimension fixed effects model with exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects as suggested by the gravity literature. As it was previously argued, the higher effects of backward (relative to forward) and services (relative to goods) on signing a deep trade agreement are verified in both the probit and the linear probability model. However, while most of the variables are insignificant in the high dimension fixed effects model, backward, forward GVC and forward GVC in services are significant, while the other variables are not. This again confirms the importance of backward GVC and service-related ones in explaining the depth of trade agreements.

Second, we examine the robustness of our results by using different dependent and independent variables (see Table 3). The first column shows an alternative definition of the agreement depth. To do so, we compare the share of legally enforceable provisions relative to the total number of provisions (legally and non-legally enforceable). In column 1 of table 3, the results show that GVC related to backward linkages and services increases the likelihood of signing a deep agreement in goods and services (in the PPML estimation, compared to column 5 in Table 1). Columns 2 to 4 present the results of the same depth definition but for the multinomial logit estimation method (where the reference category is no agreement, shallow agreement for goods, shallow agreement for goods and services and a deep agreement for goods and services). Compared to columns 1 to 3 in Table 1, the results show that GVC flows reduce the likelihood of signing a shallow agreement for goods (column 2), but increase the one for goods and services (column 3), pointing out the importance of services for GVC. Yet, the results for deep agreements are not statistically significant (column 4).

Finally, we also use an alternative measure of GVC in columns 5-7 in Table 3. In fact, instead of using the GVC level, we use the share of GVC in the total bilateral trade between the origin and destination. Globally, the results remain the same for overall GVC, GVC in services, GVC in goods, backward linkages (goods and services), with a counterintuitive effect for forward GVC.

In a nutshell, in our preferred specification relying on the PPML estimation method, our results show that GVC in general and especially those related to backward linkages and to services matter in signing deep trade agreements that go beyond trade liberalization. This result holds in different types of estimation methods (probit, HDFE and multinomial logit) and alternative measures of GVC (level and shares) and depth.

4.3 Extensions

After examining the overall effect of GVC on signing deep trade agreements, we extend the analysis in three ways. First, we see whether there are some provisions that are likely to be included in an agreement thanks to GVC. Second, we analyze how the development level helps explain the impact of GVC on signing deep agreement. To do so, we take into account the development level of the exporter and the importer and whether they have the same development level or not. Finally, as mentioned before, we distinguish between the vertical and the horizontal depth of agreements.

4.3.1 On the Heterogeneity of Provisions

Deep trade agreements can include a host of trade and non-trade related provisions. The DTA database distinguishes between WTO-related provisions (WTO+) and those that are not related to the scope of WTO (WTOX). In the first group, which is more likely to be affected by GVC, most of the provisions are related to services, NTMs and institutions. This is why Table 4 presents the three types of provisions. While different types of GVC categories of matter for these provisions, there is some heterogeneity. First, all coefficients are positive and statistically significant, with the exception of those related to forward GVC in services. Second, the impact of GVC related flows on the depth of NTM (SPS, TBT, etc.) provisions is higher than that of services (GATS, TRIPS, TRIMS, etc.) followed by those of institutions (state aid, procurement). This finding applies to all types of GVCs with the same orders of magnitude mentioned before, i.e. the highest coefficients are those of backward GVC in services, followed by backward GVC in goods, and finally forward GVC in goods.

These results, thus, confirm three important facts. With the decrease in tariffs in several countries (with the exception of the trade wars that started in 2017), more attention has been attributed to NTMs that might be more protectionist than tariffs. Thus, higher levels of GVCs might require a more stringent commitment from trading partners not to impose arbitrary NTMs or to regulate their services. Our results corroborate those of Bondi et al. (2025) who show that GVC increases the probability of signing deep PTAs that include provisions aiming at regulating trade policies. This is particularly important in the case of imported inputs that are significantly affected by NTMs and thus can affect the whole supply chain (Webb et al. (2020) and Ghodsi (2023)). A similar argument holds for services provisions that can become deeper for higher levels of service-dependent GVCs. Finally, it is important to note that WTO related provisions are

globally significant, while WTOX are not. This confirms the fact that the latter might not really matter for GVCs and thus are not deeply negotiated between trading partners.

4.3.2 Does the Development Level Matter?

The impact of GVC on signing a deeper level of trade agreement depends on the development level of trade partners. One can expect that developed countries with better and similar institutions are more likely to sign deep trade agreements. However, given that most of the GVC flows take place between developing and developed countries, we can argue that this GVC channel represents a new motive to sign deep trade agreements between countries belonging to different income groups. This can indeed overcome the problem of deficient institutions in developing countries as deep trade agreements should represent a solid framework of cooperation.

Panel (a) of Table 5 shows that, while the impact of overall GVCs is negative, the interaction with a high-income exporter and a low-income importer is positive and statistically significant, with a positive net effect of GVCs on signing a deep trade agreement. Yet, if both the exporter and the importer belong to the low-income category, the impact of GVCs becomes higher⁶. This is in line with Stiller (2023) who shows that when firms in a country are highly dependent on inputs from a negotiating partner, the impact of economic strength decreases with the degree of reliance of its businesses on that country. When comparing different types of GVCs, our previous findings still hold given that the highest impact is the one of GVC flows in services followed by those in goods. Moreover, the impact of backward flows have a greater impact than forward ones.

Panel (b) extends this analysis by comparing the impact of GVC on signing a deep trade agreement for countries that belong to similar income groups (relative to those that belong to different income groups). Generally, belonging to similar income groups reduces the positive effect of GVCs. This impact can be attributed to two main reasons. First, given that most of the GVC flows take place between developing and developed countries, the latter might need to secure their imported inputs, pushing them to sign deep trade agreements. Second, generally, developed countries, having a stronger bargaining power in trade negotiations, are more likely to impose deeper trade agreements. This result validates our hypothesis according to which GVC flows create a new motive to deepen trade agreements between countries that belong to different income groups.

⁶These results are confirmed in Tables A.3 that splits the sample by income level as only the coefficient so High-Low and Low-Low are significant. Tables A.4 A.9 combines the results of the development level and the heterogeneity of provisions to show how GVC affects the depth of different provisions for different income levels. Globally, WTO-related provisions are significant, while WTOX are not

4.3.3 Vertical Depth

Finally, we would like to examine how GVC affects the two types of agreement depth as the literature distinguishes between horizontal depth (that refers to whether trade agreements go beyond the simple tariff reduction) and vertical depth (whether they include legally enforceable provisions that deepen countries integration). It the latter might also represent a substitute for weak institutions that might characterize developing countries as the legal enforceability of the agreement will be guaranteed. Table 6 shows that most of the estimated coefficients are not statistically significant, with the exception of the one of GVC backward flows in services (though at 10%) and the one of forward services (negative and significant at 10%). However, more interesting results are obtained when we control for the development level in Table 7. As it was mentioned before, vertically deep agreements are more likely to be signed between low income countries on the one hand and between a high-income exporting country and a low-income importing one⁷ and, on the other hand, between low countries. Our previous results also hold given that backward flows and those related to services exert a greater impact on signing a deep trade agreement.

5 Conclusion

This paper attempts to investigate how GVC integration affects the depth of trade agreements. We, thus, contribute to the literature in two ways. First, we extend the analysis of Fontagné and Santoni (2021) by taking into account the depth of trade agreements. Second, we do not limit the analysis to overall GVC but we investigate the differences in the GVC position (backward vs. forward participation) and the sector involved (goods vs. services). To test these hypotheses, we combine different data sources (Eora dataset and the Deep Trade Agreement database).

Our main findings show that GVC increases the likelihood of signing a deep agreement that focuses on goods and services. More particularly, the effect of backward linkages (relative to forward) and service-related GVC (relative to good) are more likely to affect the depth of the agreement. These two findings are of particular importance given the servicification of the manufacturing sector and the increasing reliance of GVC on services. In addition, backward GVC related flows provide access to competitively priced inputs and more varieties (Baldwin and Lopez-Gonzalez (2015)). These results remain robust after running a battery of sensitivity tests. In addition, we show that

⁷These results are confirmed by Table A.10 that splits the sample by development level and that shows that the vertical depth is affected by GVCs in the case of countries that belong to different income groups, especially exporting high-income countries and importing low-income ones.

the impact of GVC is higher on the depth of provisions related to NTMs followed by services. When the development level is considered, countries belonging to different levels of development are more likely to sign deep trade agreements.

From a policy perspective, our paper has three implications. First, we provide a new determinant that can explain the depth of trade agreements, especially between dissimilar countries that are vertically integrated. As the literature has shown the limited impact of shallow agreements, and given the increasing involvement of different countries in GVCs, the higher the GVC, the more likely the countries should need deeper trade agreements that go beyond the simple tariffs reduction. Second, given that developing countries are increasingly involved in GVC, they might have a bargaining power to deepen trade agreements to expand the latter beyond goods. Indeed, having a comparative advantage in services, the latter must be part of the trade agreements. Finally, from the developed countries perspective, given the uncertainty that countries face, trade agreements can constitute a powerful tool to stabilize supply chains, especially in a turbulent times where uncertainty dominates trade policy (Limão and Maggi (2015)). Indeed, governments might stronger incentives to sign trade agreements (and especially deep ones) when the trading environment is more uncertain.

Table 1: PTA and GVC - Baseline results with Multinomial Logit and PPML

	Mlogit			PPML -	PPML -
	Shallow G	Shallow G&S	Deep G&S	<i>positive values</i> $Depth_{le}^{max}$	<i>all</i> $Depth_{le}^{max}$
GVC	-0.1376*** (0.026)	-0.0723 (0.073)	0.3882*** (0.041)	0.0083*** (0.003)	0.0291*** (0.010)
GVC services	-0.1381*** (0.029)	-0.2218*** (0.071)	0.5537*** (0.047)	0.0024 (0.003)	0.0183* (0.010)
GVC goods	-0.1324*** (0.024)	-0.0368 (0.068)	0.2901*** (0.039)	0.0088*** (0.003)	0.0284*** (0.009)
GVC backward	-0.1140*** (0.022)	-0.0555 (0.062)	0.3726*** (0.033)	0.0083*** (0.003)	0.0322*** (0.010)
GVC backward services	-0.0870*** (0.021)	-0.0916* (0.047)	0.4355*** (0.035)	0.0031 (0.003)	0.0321*** (0.010)
GVC backward goods	-0.1148*** (0.021)	-0.0443 (0.062)	0.3110*** (0.033)	0.0086*** (0.003)	0.0298*** (0.010)
GVC forward	-0.0862*** (0.023)	0.0221 (0.086)	0.3308*** (0.042)	0.0066** (0.003)	0.0172* (0.010)
GVC forward services	-0.0786*** (0.028)	-0.0541 (0.090)	0.4090*** (0.046)	0.0001 (0.003)	-0.0039 (0.011)
GVC forward goods	-0.0758*** (0.024)	-0.0651 (0.069)	0.2088*** (0.040)	0.0077*** (0.003)	0.0176* (0.009)
Controls	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
FE	t	t	t	it and jt	it and jt
Observations	730,429	730,429	730,429	128,227	612,587

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) FE stands for fixed effects, t stands for time, i for exporter and j for importer fixed effects

Table 2: Robustness Checks - Alternative Estimation Methods

	Probit	LMP	OLS
	$Depth_{le}^{max}$	$Depth_{le}^{max}$	$Depth_{le}^{max}$
GVC	0.1573*** (0.020)	0.0169*** (0.004)	0.0033 (0.000)
GVC services	0.1900*** (0.023)	0.0171*** (0.005)	0.0020 (0.000)
GVC goods	0.1357*** (0.019)	0.0153*** (0.004)	0.0035 (0.000)
GVC backward	0.1417*** (0.017)	0.0132*** (0.003)	0.0039*** (0.001)
GVC backward services	0.1472*** (0.018)	0.0110*** (0.003)	0.0019 (0.000)
GVC backward goods	0.1278*** (0.017)	0.0124*** (0.003)	0.0041 (0.000)
GVC forward	0.1261*** (0.020)	0.0073* (0.004)	0.0035*** (0.001)
GVC forward services	0.1023*** (0.023)	0.0097** (0.004)	0.0024*** (0.001)
GVC forward goods	0.1174*** (0.021)	0.0078** (0.004)	0.0039 (0.000)
Controls	YES	YES	YES
FE	t	t	it and jt
Observations	733,033	128,385	128,387

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) FE stands for fixed effects, t for time, i for exporter and j for importer fixed effects

Table 3: Robustness Checks - Alternative Variables

	PPML	Mlogit			Mlogit Shares		
	$Depth_{ie}$	Shallow G	Shallow G&S	Deep G&S	Shallow G	Shallow G&S	Deep G&S
GVC	0.0255*** (0.010)	-0.1376*** (0.026)	0.3865*** (0.041)	0.0301 (0.065)	-2.6797*** (0.169)	-1.6294*** (0.337)	2.4989*** (0.137)
GVC services	0.0158 (0.011)	-0.1383*** (0.029)	0.5666*** (0.046)	-0.0499 (0.068)	-2.1008*** (0.340)	-3.5049*** (0.786)	1.5608*** (0.314)
GVC goods	0.0252*** (0.009)	-0.1322*** (0.024)	0.2765*** (0.040)	0.0391 (0.059)	-2.6311*** (0.194)	-1.4704*** (0.483)	2.2989*** (0.155)
GVC backward	0.0309*** (0.010)	-0.1145*** (0.022)	0.3769*** (0.035)	0.0426 (0.053)	-2.1533*** (0.174)	-0.8983*** (0.325)	2.4166*** (0.128)
GVC backward services	0.0305*** (0.010)	-0.0881*** (0.021)	0.4409*** (0.036)	0.0058 (0.045)	-1.6387*** (0.508)	-2.8693*** (0.969)	1.6844*** (0.394)
GVC backward goods	0.0288*** (0.009)	-0.1151*** (0.021)	0.3048*** (0.035)	0.0443 (0.052)	-2.2568*** (0.197)	-1.0128** (0.420)	2.3144*** (0.136)
GVC forward	0.0147 (0.010)	-0.0860*** (0.023)	0.3537*** (0.046)	0.0630 (0.065)	-0.5949*** (0.204)	-0.7368 (0.613)	-2.7563*** (0.276)
GVC forward services	-0.0045 (0.011)	-0.0789*** (0.028)	0.4365*** (0.047)	0.0237 (0.072)	-0.5117 (0.452)	-2.5637* (1.453)	-4.0867*** (0.635)
GVC forward goods	0.0161* (0.009)	-0.0753*** (0.024)	0.1910*** (0.044)	0.0008 (0.055)	-0.5009* (0.283)	-0.0477 (0.822)	-4.2157*** (0.405)
Controls	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
FE	it and jt	t	t	t	t	t	t
Observations	612,586	730,429	730,429	730,429	723,982	723,982	723,982

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) FE stands for fixed effects, t stands for time, i for exporter and j for importer fixed effects

Table 4: PTA, GVC and Heterogeneity of Provisions

	NTMs	Institutions	Services	WTO+	WTOX
GVC	0.0465*** (0.010)	0.0393*** (0.012)	0.0426*** (0.010)	0.0428*** (0.010)	-0.0049 (0.010)
GVC services	0.0366*** (0.011)	0.0323** (0.013)	0.0316*** (0.011)	0.0335*** (0.011)	-0.0152 (0.010)
GVC goods	0.0451*** (0.010)	0.0373*** (0.011)	0.0395*** (0.010)	0.0408*** (0.010)	-0.0038 (0.009)
GVC backward	0.0493*** (0.010)	0.0368*** (0.012)	0.0390*** (0.010)	0.0437*** (0.010)	0.0013 (0.010)
GVC backward services	0.0501*** (0.011)	0.0455*** (0.012)	0.0416*** (0.011)	0.0470*** (0.011)	-0.0007 (0.010)
GVC backward goods	0.0462*** (0.010)	0.0333*** (0.012)	0.0355*** (0.010)	0.0402*** (0.010)	0.0004 (0.010)
GVC forward	0.0344*** (0.010)	0.0212* (0.012)	0.0306*** (0.010)	0.0294*** (0.011)	-0.0133 (0.010)
GVC forward services	0.0135 (0.012)	0.0001 (0.014)	0.0094 (0.012)	0.0082 (0.012)	-0.0315*** (0.010)
GVC forward goods	0.0337*** (0.010)	0.0206* (0.011)	0.0257*** (0.010)	0.0277*** (0.010)	-0.0100 (0.009)
Observations	587,703	497,431	410,610	587,703	532,335

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects.

Table 5: PTA, GVC and Development Level

	(a) Income group			(b) Similar income group			
	GVC	GVC services	GVC goods	GVC	GVC services	GVC goods	
GVC	-0.0462*** (0.011)	-0.0581*** (0.011)	-0.0449*** (0.010)	GVC	0.0609*** (0.009)	0.0634*** (0.010)	0.0579*** (0.009)
GVC*High-Low	0.1004*** (0.005)	0.1156*** (0.006)	0.0963*** (0.005)	GVC*sim.	-0.0819*** (0.005)	-0.0961*** (0.005)	-0.0787*** (0.004)
GVC*Low-Low	0.1923*** (0.013)	0.2130*** (0.014)	0.1834*** (0.013)				
Obs.	612,585	612,893	612,551	Obs.	612,585	612,893	612,551
	GVC backward	GVC back. ser.	GVC back. goods	GVC backward	GVC back. services	GVC back. goods	
GVC	-0.0424*** (0.011)	-0.0511*** (0.011)	-0.0424*** (0.010)	GVC	0.0643*** (0.010)	0.0751*** (0.010)	0.0605*** (0.009)
GVC*High-Low	0.1004*** (0.005)	0.1205*** (0.006)	0.0970*** (0.005)	GVC*sim.	-0.0808*** (0.004)	-0.0953*** (0.005)	-0.0788*** (0.004)
GVC*Low-Low	0.1850*** (0.013)	0.2013*** (0.013)	0.1777*** (0.012)				
Obs.	612,676	613,239	612,612	Obs.	612,676	613,239	612,612
	GVC forward	GVC for. ser.	GVC for. goods	GVC forward	GVC for. ser.	GVC for. goods	
GVC	-0.0511*** (0.010)	-0.0672*** (0.011)	-0.0487*** (0.010)	GVC	0.0516*** (0.010)	0.0435*** (0.011)	0.0485*** (0.009)
GVC*High-Low	0.0985*** (0.005)	0.1084*** (0.006)	0.0927*** (0.005)	GVC*sim.	-0.0817*** (0.005)	-0.0919*** (0.005)	-0.0766*** (0.004)
GVC*Low-Low	0.1939*** (0.013)	0.2145*** (0.015)	0.1834*** (0.013)				
Obs.	607,329	609,386	604,679	Obs.	607,329	609,386	604,679

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects

Table 6: PTA, GVC and Vertical Depth

	LE enforc.
GVC	0.0119 (0.009)
GVC services	0.0035 (0.010)
GVC goods	0.0107 (0.009)
GVC backward	0.0134 (0.009)
GVC backward services	0.0184* (0.010)
GVC backward goods	0.0103 (0.009)
GVC forward	0.0010 (0.009)
GVC forward services	-0.0191* (0.010)
GVC forward goods	0.0010 (0.009)
Observations	612,585

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects

Table 7: PTA, GVC and Vertical Depth - with Development Level

	Interaction with income		
	Overall	Backward	Forward
GVC	-0.0647*** (0.010)	-0.0623*** (0.010)	-0.0673*** (0.010)
GVC*High-Low	0.1032*** (0.005)	0.1033*** (0.005)	0.1002*** (0.005)
GVC*Low-Low	0.1945*** (0.014)	0.1873*** (0.013)	0.1936*** (0.014)
GVC services	-0.0722*** (0.010)	-0.0645*** (0.010)	-0.0809*** (0.011)
GVC services*High-Low	0.1171*** (0.006)	0.1222*** (0.006)	0.1094*** (0.006)
GVC services*Low-Low	0.2108*** (0.015)	0.2001*** (0.013)	0.2110*** (0.015)
GVC goods	-0.0641*** (0.010)	-0.0632*** (0.010)	-0.0656*** (0.010)
GVC goods*High-Low	0.0993*** (0.005)	0.1000*** (0.005)	0.0945*** (0.005)
GVC goods*Low-Low	0.1861*** (0.013)	0.1801*** (0.013)	0.1841*** (0.013)
Interaction with same category			
	Overall	Backward	Forward
GVC	0.0460*** (0.009)	0.0481*** (0.009)	0.0382*** (0.009)
GVC*same cat.	-0.0898*** (0.004)	-0.0888*** (0.004)	-0.0887*** (0.004)
GVC services	0.0520*** (0.010)	0.0644*** (0.009)	0.0323*** (0.010)
GVC services*same cat.	-0.1037*** (0.005)	-0.1032*** (0.005)	-0.0988*** (0.005)
GVC goods	0.0425*** (0.009)	0.0436*** (0.009)	0.0343*** (0.009)
GVC goods*same cat.	-0.0866*** (0.004)	-0.0867*** (0.004)	-0.0834*** (0.004)

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects

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A Descriptive Statistics

Table A.1: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
GVC				
Share in bilateral trade	0.41158	0.15577	0.00006	0.99999
Share in total trade	0.00254	0.01187	0.00000	0.71058
Bilateral level (in log)	13.56228	2.80557	4.50934	26.05455
GVC services				
Share in bilateral trade	0.11690	0.08265	0.00011	0.99535
Share in total trade	0.00051	0.00280	0.00000	0.34352
Bilateral level (in log)	12.10590	2.49226	4.34797	24.24685
GVC goods				
Share in bilateral trade	0.29956	0.13579	0.00016	0.99957
Share in total trade	0.00202	0.01014	0.00000	0.56450
Bilateral level (in log)	13.20366	2.88579	4.08746	26.02772
GVC Backward				
Share in bilateral trade	0.23677	0.13858	0.00065	0.99995
Share in total trade	0.00142	0.00784	0.00000	0.93517
Bilateral level (in log)	12.93295	2.86180	5.40613	25.82758
GVC Backward services				
Share in bilateral trade	0.05049	0.05667	0.00006	0.99603
Share in total trade	0.00024	0.00182	0.00000	0.45867
Bilateral level (in log)	11.14641	2.61206	4.07337	22.63145
GVC Backward goods				
Share in bilateral trade	0.19198	0.12796	0.00076	0.99956
Share in total trade	0.00118	0.00677	0.00000	0.62482
Bilateral level (in log)	12.66910	2.90755	6.34986	25.80297
GVC Forward				
Share in bilateral trade	0.17520	0.12327	0.00003	0.99784
Share in total trade	0.00115	0.00626	0.00000	0.32969
Bilateral level (in log)	12.53394	2.793459	0.83732	25.39173
GVC Forward services				
Share in bilateral trade	0.06681	0.05886	0.00010	0.68758
Share in total trade	0.00028	0.00181	0.00000	0.17298
Bilateral level (in log)	11.41198	2.49314	0.93883	24.10015
GVC Forward goods				
Share in bilateral trade	0.10910	0.08573	0.00001	0.99838
Share in total trade	0.00087	0.00523	0.00000	0.32958
Bilateral level (in log)	12.02896	2.90615	1.88151	25.07694
Depth				
$Depth_{le}$	0.16448	0.36021	0.00000	1.00000
$Depth_{le}^{max}$	0.03905	0.11718	0.00000	0.71154

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

B Control Variables

Table A.2: Results of Control Variables

	Mlogit			Probit	LPM
	Shallow G	Shallow G&S	Deep G&S	Deep G&S	Deep G&S
GDP sum	-0.0813*** (0.030)	1.7724*** (0.096)	-0.7361*** (0.078)	-0.4041*** (0.026)	-0.0062 (0.005)
GDP sim	0.2717*** (0.037)	-0.6001*** (0.134)	0.6339*** (0.106)	0.2548*** (0.040)	0.0277** (0.012)
Diff(K/L)	-0.1847*** (0.035)	0.2575** (0.110)	-0.1262 (0.098)	-0.0448 (0.043)	-0.0176** (0.008)
Diff(K/L) sq.	0.0180* (0.009)	-0.0383 (0.029)	-0.2021*** (0.034)	-0.0748*** (0.014)	-0.0009 (0.002)
Natural	1.2945*** (0.034)	1.7740*** (0.053)	1.4289*** (0.040)	0.5212*** (0.017)	
Remote	3.3019*** (0.140)	4.8352*** (0.192)	3.3525*** (0.179)	0.0595 (0.073)	
Nb. RTAi	0.0543*** (0.001)	0.0467*** (0.002)	0.0607*** (0.001)	0.0173*** (0.000)	0.0003*** (0.000)
Nb RTAj	0.0540*** (0.001)	0.0473*** (0.002)	0.0639*** (0.001)	0.0188*** (0.000)	0.0003*** (0.000)
GDP sum (mean)	0.1387*** (0.031)	-1.8750*** (0.098)	0.4573*** (0.080)	0.2708*** (0.027)	
GDP sim (mean)	-0.1214*** (0.038)	0.6134*** (0.134)	-0.6653*** (0.105)	-0.2335*** (0.040)	
Diff(K/L) (mean)	0.0699 (0.076)	0.0327 (0.180)	0.1313 (0.134)	0.1414** (0.056)	
Diff(K/L) sq. (mean)	-0.0701*** (0.019)	-0.0857* (0.049)	0.0302 (0.042)	-0.0063 (0.017)	
Observations	730,429	730,429	730,429	733,033	128,385

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) The estimation method is mentioned in the first row

C Further Results

Table A.3: PTA, GVC and Development Level - by income category

	High-Low	High-High	Low-Low	Same cat.
GVC	0.0509*** (0.011)	0.0133 (0.014)	0.0663*** (0.018)	-0.0064 (0.013)
GVC services	0.0519*** (0.012)	0.0046 (0.014)	0.0611*** (0.019)	-0.0199 (0.012)
GVC goods	0.0487*** (0.011)	0.0149 (0.014)	0.0628*** (0.017)	-0.0054 (0.012)
GVC backward	0.0557*** (0.011)	0.0153 (0.015)	0.0632*** (0.017)	-0.0038 (0.013)
GVC backward services	0.0612*** (0.012)	0.0115 (0.014)	0.0634*** (0.017)	-0.0037 (0.012)
GVC backward goods	0.0529*** (0.011)	0.0162 (0.014)	0.0573*** (0.017)	-0.0060 (0.013)
GVC forward	0.0428*** (0.011)	0.0133 (0.014)	0.0641*** (0.019)	-0.0128 (0.012)
GVC forward services	0.0391*** (0.012)	-0.0026 (0.013)	0.0539** (0.021)	-0.0399*** (0.012)
GVC forward goods	0.0396*** (0.011)	0.0150 (0.013)	0.0637*** (0.018)	-0.0087 (0.012)
Observations	442,668	76,859	67,634	144,493

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects.

Table A.4: PTA, GVC and Heterogeneity of Provisions - by development level I

	High-Low				
	NTMs	Institutions	Services	WTO+	WTOX
GVC	0.0544*** (0.011)	0.0740*** (0.013)	0.0783*** (0.013)	0.0608*** (0.011)	0.0191 (0.012)
GVC services	0.0531*** (0.012)	0.0817*** (0.014)	0.0831*** (0.014)	0.0628*** (0.012)	0.0209 (0.013)
GVC goods	0.0527*** (0.011)	0.0715*** (0.013)	0.0745*** (0.012)	0.0584*** (0.011)	0.0171 (0.012)
GVC backward	0.0598*** (0.011)	0.0721*** (0.013)	0.0744*** (0.013)	0.0637*** (0.011)	0.0274** (0.013)
GVC backward services	0.0633*** (0.012)	0.0865*** (0.014)	0.0849*** (0.013)	0.0710*** (0.012)	0.0329** (0.013)
GVC backward goods	0.0571*** (0.011)	0.0697*** (0.013)	0.0719*** (0.013)	0.0609*** (0.011)	0.0245** (0.012)
GVC forward	0.0468*** (0.011)	0.0650*** (0.013)	0.0734*** (0.013)	0.0535*** (0.011)	0.0095 (0.012)
GVC forward services	0.0385*** (0.013)	0.0676*** (0.015)	0.0742*** (0.015)	0.0491*** (0.013)	0.0097 (0.014)
GVC forward goods	0.0443*** (0.011)	0.0600*** (0.013)	0.0655*** (0.012)	0.0494*** (0.011)	0.0074 (0.012)
Observations	423,754	327,830	272,134	423,754	353,956
	Low-Low				
	NTMs	Institutions	Services	WTO+	WTOX
GVC	0.0612*** (0.017)	0.0726*** (0.024)	0.0776*** (0.022)	0.0731*** (0.017)	0.0394* (0.021)
GVC services	0.0552*** (0.019)	0.0802*** (0.025)	0.0447* (0.024)	0.0665*** (0.019)	0.0381* (0.022)
GVC goods	0.0576*** (0.017)	0.0667*** (0.024)	0.0836*** (0.022)	0.0698*** (0.017)	0.0363* (0.021)
GVC backward	0.0582*** (0.017)	0.0692*** (0.023)	0.0690*** (0.022)	0.0693*** (0.017)	0.0382* (0.020)
GVC backward services	0.0599*** (0.017)	0.0719*** (0.023)	0.0410* (0.021)	0.0680*** (0.017)	0.0426** (0.020)
GVC backward goods	0.0518*** (0.017)	0.0647*** (0.023)	0.0762*** (0.022)	0.0643*** (0.017)	0.0313 (0.020)
GVC forward	0.0565*** (0.019)	0.0771*** (0.026)	0.0884*** (0.024)	0.0719*** (0.019)	0.0346 (0.022)
GVC forward services	0.0414* (0.021)	0.0974*** (0.028)	0.0612** (0.026)	0.0605*** (0.021)	0.0274 (0.024)
GVC forward goods	0.0575*** (0.018)	0.0678*** (0.025)	0.0877*** (0.023)	0.0710*** (0.018)	0.0364* (0.021)
Observations	63,423	41,890	26,498	63,484	48,743

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects.

Table A.5: PTA, GVC and Heterogeneity of Provisions - by development level II

	High-High				
	NTMs	Institutions	Services	WTO+	WTOX
GVC	0.0369** (0.016)	0.0123 (0.013)	0.0276** (0.014)	0.0302** (0.015)	-0.0081 (0.016)
GVC services	0.0200 (0.016)	0.0129 (0.013)	0.0280** (0.014)	0.0215 (0.014)	-0.0138 (0.014)
GVC goods	0.0384** (0.016)	0.0112 (0.012)	0.0250* (0.013)	0.0301** (0.014)	-0.0051 (0.015)
GVC backward	0.0399** (0.017)	0.0120 (0.013)	0.0262* (0.014)	0.0313** (0.015)	-0.0052 (0.016)
GVC backward services	0.0288* (0.016)	0.0181 (0.013)	0.0312** (0.014)	0.0283** (0.014)	-0.0078 (0.014)
GVC backward goods	0.0405** (0.016)	0.0108 (0.012)	0.0238* (0.013)	0.0308** (0.014)	-0.0030 (0.016)
GVC forward	0.0319** (0.016)	0.0115 (0.013)	0.0264** (0.013)	0.0270* (0.014)	-0.0034 (0.015)
GVC forward services	0.0085 (0.016)	0.0040 (0.013)	0.0203 (0.014)	0.0113 (0.014)	-0.0167 (0.014)
GVC forward goods	0.0329** (0.015)	0.0106 (0.012)	0.0217* (0.012)	0.0259* (0.013)	0.0001 (0.014)
Observations	76,759	69,799	65,529	76,859	70,063
	Same cat.				
	NTMs	Institutions	Services	WTO+	WTOX
GVC	0.0160 (0.013)	-0.0195 (0.013)	0.0021 (0.013)	0.0075 (0.013)	-0.0220 (0.014)
GVC services	-0.0020 (0.013)	-0.0247* (0.013)	-0.0031 (0.014)	-0.0059 (0.013)	-0.0312** (0.013)
GVC goods	0.0157 (0.012)	-0.0213* (0.012)	-0.0004 (0.013)	0.0064 (0.012)	-0.0190 (0.014)
GVC backward	0.0183 (0.013)	-0.0181 (0.013)	0.0008 (0.013)	0.0090 (0.012)	-0.0185 (0.014)
GVC backward services	0.0153 (0.012)	-0.0086 (0.013)	0.0074 (0.013)	0.0110 (0.012)	-0.0188 (0.013)
GVC backward goods	0.0146 (0.013)	-0.0227* (0.012)	-0.0033 (0.013)	0.0048 (0.012)	-0.0182 (0.014)
GVC forward	0.0057 (0.013)	-0.0278** (0.013)	-0.0021 (0.013)	-0.0018 (0.012)	-0.0223* (0.013)
GVC forward services	-0.0264** (0.013)	-0.0482*** (0.014)	-0.0193 (0.014)	-0.0300** (0.013)	-0.0429*** (0.013)
GVC forward goods	0.0088 (0.012)	-0.0262** (0.012)	-0.0053 (0.012)	-0.0006 (0.012)	-0.0166 (0.013)
Observations	140,182	111,689	92,020	140,343	118,806

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii)*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects.

Table A.6: PTA, GVC and Heterogeneity of Provisions - interaction with development level I

	Overall GVC					
	LE enfirorc.	NTMs	Institutions	Services	WTO+	WTOX
GVC	-0.0647*** (0.010)	-0.0263** (0.012)	-0.0615*** (0.013)	-0.0535*** (0.011)	-0.0443*** (0.012)	-0.0620*** (0.010)
GVC*High-Low	0.1032*** (0.005)	0.0878*** (0.006)	0.1397*** (0.006)	0.1451*** (0.007)	0.1118*** (0.006)	0.0832*** (0.005)
GVC*Low-Low	0.1945*** (0.014)	0.1574*** (0.012)	0.2494*** (0.018)	0.2021*** (0.021)	0.1969*** (0.013)	0.1925*** (0.015)
GVC services	-0.0722*** (0.010)	-0.0412*** (0.012)	-0.0689*** (0.014)	-0.0604*** (0.011)	-0.0563*** (0.012)	-0.0699*** (0.010)
GVC services*High-Low	0.1171*** (0.006)	0.1014*** (0.007)	0.1574*** (0.007)	0.1624*** (0.008)	0.1272*** (0.006)	0.0955*** (0.006)
GVC services*Low-Low	0.2108*** (0.015)	0.1793*** (0.013)	0.2834*** (0.020)	0.2072*** (0.023)	0.2197*** (0.014)	0.2063*** (0.017)
GVC goods	-0.0641*** (0.010)	-0.0252** (0.011)	-0.0612*** (0.013)	-0.0552*** (0.011)	-0.0440*** (0.011)	-0.0594*** (0.010)
GVC goods*High-Low	0.0993*** (0.005)	0.0844*** (0.006)	0.1351*** (0.006)	0.1402*** (0.007)	0.1079*** (0.006)	0.0794*** (0.005)
GVC goods*Low-Low	0.1861*** (0.013)	0.1496*** (0.012)	0.2372*** (0.017)	0.1950*** (0.020)	0.1880*** (0.012)	0.1845*** (0.015)

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii)*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects.

Table A.7: PTA, GVC and Heterogeneity of Provisions - interaction with development level II

	Backward GVC					
	LE enfirorc.	NTMs	Institutions	Services	WTO+	WTOX
GVC	-0.0623*** (0.010)	-0.0225* (0.012)	-0.0629*** (0.013)	-0.0557*** (0.011)	-0.0422*** (0.011)	-0.0559*** (0.010)
GVC*High-Low	0.1033*** (0.005)	0.0876*** (0.006)	0.1397*** (0.006)	0.1441*** (0.007)	0.1117*** (0.006)	0.0839*** (0.005)
GVC*Low-Low	0.1873*** (0.013)	0.1519*** (0.012)	0.2429*** (0.017)	0.1965*** (0.020)	0.1904*** (0.012)	0.1842*** (0.015)
GVC services	-0.0645*** (0.010)	-0.0322*** (0.012)	-0.0641*** (0.014)	-0.0587*** (0.011)	-0.0494*** (0.012)	-0.0618*** (0.010)
GVC services*High-Low	0.1222*** (0.006)	0.1034*** (0.007)	0.1620*** (0.007)	0.1682*** (0.008)	0.1310*** (0.007)	0.1014*** (0.006)
GVC services*Low-Low	0.2001*** (0.013)	0.1685*** (0.012)	0.2646*** (0.018)	0.2037*** (0.020)	0.2072*** (0.013)	0.1955*** (0.015)
GVC goods	-0.0632*** (0.010)	-0.0229** (0.011)	-0.0636*** (0.013)	-0.0571*** (0.011)	-0.0430*** (0.011)	-0.0550*** (0.010)
GVC goods*High-Low	0.1000*** (0.005)	0.0847*** (0.006)	0.1361*** (0.006)	0.1402*** (0.007)	0.1084*** (0.006)	0.0806*** (0.005)
GVC goods*Low-Low	0.1801*** (0.013)	0.1454*** (0.011)	0.2333*** (0.017)	0.1897*** (0.020)	0.1832*** (0.012)	0.1771*** (0.015)
	Forward GVC					
	LE enfirorc.	NTMs	Institutions	Services	WTO+	WTOX
GVC	-0.0673*** (0.010)	-0.0331*** (0.012)	-0.0676*** (0.013)	-0.0566*** (0.011)	-0.0503*** (0.012)	-0.0637*** (0.010)
GVC*High-Low	0.1002*** (0.005)	0.0873*** (0.006)	0.1354*** (0.006)	0.1427*** (0.007)	0.1103*** (0.006)	0.0799*** (0.005)
GVC*Low-Low	0.1936*** (0.014)	0.1584*** (0.012)	0.2526*** (0.018)	0.2012*** (0.022)	0.1983*** (0.013)	0.1956*** (0.016)
GVC services	-0.0809*** (0.011)	-0.0534*** (0.012)	-0.0809*** (0.014)	-0.0671*** (0.012)	-0.0675*** (0.012)	-0.0758*** (0.010)
GVC services*High-Low	0.1094*** (0.006)	0.0968*** (0.006)	0.1484*** (0.007)	0.1533*** (0.008)	0.1207*** (0.006)	0.0878*** (0.006)
GVC services*Low-Low	0.2110*** (0.015)	0.1784*** (0.013)	0.2946*** (0.020)	0.2065*** (0.025)	0.2211*** (0.014)	0.2121*** (0.017)
GVC goods	-0.0656*** (0.010)	-0.0312*** (0.011)	-0.0663*** (0.013)	-0.0602*** (0.010)	-0.0495*** (0.011)	-0.0594*** (0.010)
GVC goods*High-Low	0.0945*** (0.005)	0.0822*** (0.006)	0.1282*** (0.006)	0.1354*** (0.007)	0.1043*** (0.006)	0.0749*** (0.005)
GVC goods*Low-Low	0.1841*** (0.013)	0.1497*** (0.012)	0.2370*** (0.017)	0.1930*** (0.020)	0.1876*** (0.012)	0.1858*** (0.015)
Observations	612,585	587,703	497,431	410,610	587,703	532,335

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects.

Table A.8: PTA, GVC and Heterogeneity of Provisions - interaction with similarity I

	Overall GVC					
	LE enfororc.	NTMs	Institutions	Services	WTO+	WTOX
GVC	0.0460*** (0.009)	0.0682*** (0.010)	0.0910*** (0.012)	0.0990*** (0.010)	0.0757*** (0.010)	0.0273*** (0.009)
GVC*sim.	-0.0898*** (0.004)	-0.0608*** (0.005)	-0.1258*** (0.006)	-0.1380*** (0.006)	-0.0880*** (0.005)	-0.0752*** (0.005)
GVC services	0.0520*** (0.010)	0.0662*** (0.011)	0.1013*** (0.013)	0.1098*** (0.011)	0.0784*** (0.011)	0.0314*** (0.010)
GVC services*sim.	-0.1037*** (0.005)	-0.0713*** (0.005)	-0.1438*** (0.006)	-0.1570*** (0.007)	-0.1018*** (0.005)	-0.0876*** (0.005)
GVC goods	0.0425*** (0.009)	0.0656*** (0.010)	0.0862*** (0.011)	0.0922*** (0.010)	0.0718*** (0.010)	0.0260*** (0.009)
GVC goods*sim.	-0.0866*** (0.004)	-0.0587*** (0.005)	-0.1219*** (0.005)	-0.1334*** (0.006)	-0.0851*** (0.005)	-0.0719*** (0.004)

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects.

Table A.9: PTA, GVC and Heterogeneity of Provisions - interaction with similarity II

	Backward GVC					
	LE enfirorc.	NTMs	Institutions	Services	WTO+	WTOX
GVC	0.0481*** (0.009)	0.0714*** (0.010)	0.0891*** (0.012)	0.0953*** (0.010)	0.0772*** (0.010)	0.0339*** (0.010)
GVC*sim.	-0.0888*** (0.004)	-0.0597*** (0.005)	-0.1243*** (0.005)	-0.1360*** (0.006)	-0.0866*** (0.005)	-0.0750*** (0.005)
GVC services	0.0644*** (0.009)	0.0774*** (0.011)	0.1102*** (0.012)	0.1165*** (0.011)	0.0891*** (0.011)	0.0450*** (0.010)
GVC services*sim.	-0.1032*** (0.005)	-0.0680*** (0.005)	-0.1426*** (0.006)	-0.1576*** (0.007)	-0.0994*** (0.005)	-0.0892*** (0.005)
GVC goods	0.0436*** (0.009)	0.0678*** (0.010)	0.0842*** (0.012)	0.0897*** (0.010)	0.0727*** (0.010)	0.0313*** (0.009)
GVC goods*sim.	-0.0867*** (0.004)	-0.0587*** (0.005)	-0.1219*** (0.005)	-0.1328*** (0.006)	-0.0850*** (0.005)	-0.0726*** (0.004)
	Forward GVC					
	LE enfirorc.	NTMs	Institutions	Services	WTO+	WTOX
GVC	0.0382*** (0.009)	0.0580*** (0.010)	0.0774*** (0.012)	0.0921*** (0.010)	0.0652*** (0.010)	0.0209** (0.009)
GVC*sim.	-0.0887*** (0.004)	-0.0615*** (0.005)	-0.1232*** (0.006)	-0.1373*** (0.006)	-0.0882*** (0.005)	-0.0734*** (0.005)
GVC services	0.0323*** (0.010)	0.0454*** (0.012)	0.0750*** (0.014)	0.0918*** (0.012)	0.0563*** (0.012)	0.0157 (0.010)
GVC services*sim.	-0.0988*** (0.005)	-0.0700*** (0.005)	-0.1376*** (0.006)	-0.1504*** (0.007)	-0.0987*** (0.005)	-0.0822*** (0.005)
GVC goods	0.0343*** (0.009)	0.0551*** (0.010)	0.0714*** (0.011)	0.0812*** (0.010)	0.0603*** (0.010)	0.0204** (0.009)
GVC goods*sim.	-0.0834*** (0.004)	-0.0578*** (0.005)	-0.1164*** (0.005)	-0.1300*** (0.006)	-0.0832*** (0.005)	-0.0687*** (0.004)
Observations	612,585	587,703	497,431	410,610	587,703	532,335

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects.

Table A.10: Vertical Depth - by development level

	High-Low LE enfirorc.	High-High LE enfirorc.	Low-Low LE enfirorc.	Same cat. LE enfirorc.
GVC	0.0320*** (0.011)	0.0136 (0.014)	0.0667*** (0.018)	-0.0067 (0.012)
GVC services	0.0361*** (0.011)	0.0083 (0.013)	0.0608*** (0.019)	-0.0171 (0.012)
GVC goods	0.0298*** (0.010)	0.0144 (0.014)	0.0635*** (0.017)	-0.0065 (0.012)
GVC backward	0.0356*** (0.011)	0.0145 (0.014)	0.0635*** (0.017)	-0.0050 (0.012)
GVC backward services	0.0459*** (0.011)	0.0145 (0.013)	0.0631*** (0.017)	-0.0016 (0.012)
GVC backward goods	0.0324*** (0.010)	0.0148 (0.014)	0.0579*** (0.017)	-0.0077 (0.012)
GVC forward	0.0263** (0.011)	0.0141 (0.013)	0.0649*** (0.019)	-0.0125 (0.012)
GVC forward services	0.0248** (0.012)	0.0007 (0.013)	0.0538** (0.021)	-0.0370*** (0.012)
GVC forward goods	0.0232** (0.010)	0.0146 (0.013)	0.0648*** (0.018)	-0.0097 (0.012)
Observations	442,668	76,859	67,634	144,493

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

(iii) The regressions are run with a PPML estimator (with zero flows) and include all the controls.

(iv) The regressions include exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects.